

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF NURSING

Ref: SUCON 2/26 FEB/2019

Date: 27/02/2019

Sub: Minutes of the meeting of BOE (UG) Nursing Faculty:-

A meeting of the Board of examiners was held on 26/01/2019 and the following matters were discussed.

SL.No	NAME	DEPARTMENT
1.	Mrs Sathyavathi	OBG Nursing
2.	Prof. Pradeep	Medical Surgical Nursing
3.	Mrs. Sonia	Medical Surgical Nursing

AGENDA DISCUSSED	REMARKS
Approval of academic guidelines for the year 2020-21	Approved
The panel of examiners for the year of 2020-21	Approved

Dean/Chairman
BOE Nursing

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF NURSING SCIENCES

Ref: SUCON-4/NOV/2020

Date: 4/11/2020

Sub: Minutes of the meeting of BOS (UG) Nursing Faculty:-

A meeting of the BOS (UG) nursing faculty was held on 4/11/20 and the following academic matters were discussed.

SL.No	NAME	DESIGNATION
1.	Dr.N M Jose	M.Sc(N) Medical Surgical Nursing(Phd)
2.	Mrs. Sharmila	M.Sc(N) Obg Nursing

AGENDA DISCUSSED	REMARKS
Approval of academic guidelines for the year 2020-21	Approved
The panel of examiners for the year of 2020-21	Approved

DEAN NURSING

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF NURSING SCIENCES

Ref: SUCON-3/Jan /2022

Date: 3/Jan /2022

Sub: Minutes of the meeting of BOS (UG) Nursing Faculty:-

A meeting of the BOS (UG) nursing faculty was held on 3/JAN /21 and the following academic matters were discussed.

SL.No	NAME	DESIGNATION
1.	Dr.N M Jose	M.Sc(N) Medical Surgical Nursing(PhD)
2.	Mrs. Rosita Martha Rosario	M.Sc(N) Mental Health Nursing
3.	Mrs. Florin Lavina Lasrado	M.Sc(N) Child Health Nursing
4.	Mrs .Sandra Suchitha	M.Sc(N) Community health Nursing
5.	Mrs.Violet D'souza	M.Sc(N) Medical Surgical Nursing
6.	Mrs .Asha Fernandes .	M.Sc(N) Medical Surgical Nursing
7.	Mrs.Divya .K.	M.Sc(N) Obg Nursing

AGENDA DISCUSSED:

- Implementation of new syllabus guidelines for the year 21-22
- Discussed semester syllabus of theory and practical
- 4th semester is having 4 subjects
- 5th semester is having 4 subjects
- 6th semester is having 4 subjects.
- 7th semester is having 2 subjects.
- 8th semester is having internship.

DEAN NURSING

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF NURSING SCIENCES

Ref: SUCON-3/April /2022

Date: 3/ April /2022

Sub: Minutes of the meeting of BOS (UG) Nursing Faculty:-

A meeting of the BOS (UG) nursing faculty was held on 3/ April /22 and the following academic matters were discussed.

SL.No	NAME	DESIGNATION
1.	Dr.N M Jose	M.Sc(N) Medical Surgical Nursing(PhD)
2.	Mrs. Rosita Martha Rosario	M.Sc(N) Mental Health Nursing
3.	Mrs. Florin Lavina Lasrado	M.Sc(N) Child Health Nursing
4.	Mrs .Sandra Suchitha	M.Sc(N) Community health Nursing
5.	Mrs.Violet D'souza	M.Sc(N) Medical Surgical Nursing
6.	Mrs .Asha Fernandes .	M.Sc(N) Medical Surgical Nursing
7.	Mrs.Divya .K.	M.Sc(N) Obg Nursing
8.	Mrs Maria	M.Sc(N) Community health Nursing
9.	Mrs Divya Rani	M.Sc(N) Obg Nursing

AGENDA DISCUSSED:

Value added courses were introduced according to INC syllabus under following topics

- Diabetic management
- Disaster management
- Lactation management
- Menopausal health
- Personality development

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